

The Impact of Working Condition on Academic Staff Job Performance in The Niger Delta University

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Abstract

The research work focused on the implication of working condition on academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State. The researcher adopted the descriptive survey design as data were collected from a representative sample of the population. The research work was guided by three (3) research questions. A twelve item questionnaire titled The Impact of Working Condition on Academic Staff Job Performance in the Niger Delta University (TIWCASJPNDU) structured in a modified Likert Scale was used for the study to elicit for information from respondents. The population of the study comprised all eight hundred and seventy two (872) academic staff in the Niger Delta University. The sample size of the study was one hundred and seventy four academic staff representing 20% of the entire population. The random sampling technique was used to arrive at this figure. Frequency count and simple percentage were the statistical tools used in analyzing the data. The study discovered that good working condition significantly and positively impact on the job performance of academic staff in the Niger Delta University and as such recommended that academic staff should be provided with conducive working environment, motivation and regular training and development for them to be able to carry out their job effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: Working Condition, Academic Staff, Job Performance

Introduction

Working condition is very important in enhancing or reducing the performance of academic staff in Nigerian university with particular emphasis on the Niger Delta University. This is so because the working conditions of workers could affect their performance either positively or negatively, Good working condition will be very good in enhancing the performance of academic staff. While on the other hand poor working condition could lead to their poor or lack of performance. According to Vello (2019) working condition could impact on factors such as job satisfaction and staff motivation in the organization. For instance academic staff who are satisfied with their jobs will be very happy and this could positively affect their performance level which will make them to be at their very best. But on the other hand if staff are not satisfied, they will not be happy with their jobs and this could mean a decrease in their performance level. Also, the issue of motivation is very important. When it comes to the work environment the issue of staff motivation cannot be

over emphasized, as well motivated staff will always work very hard. In so doing they are very likely to be very effective, efficient and highly productive. It has been discovered over time in researches being carried out that the working condition of academic staff is a very key determinant of their level of productivity. Studies have also shown that factors like promotion, regular payment of salary, job autonomy. Good pay, recognition, fringe benefits, conducive working environment, good health care facility, training and development have essential roles in the performance level of academic staff.

According to Out (2012), promotion is a constructive means of thanking individuals for their work and service. A promotion entails taking on greater responsibility, earning more money, and gaining more status or respect. Promotions encourage employees to work very hard and raise their level of production by boosting their morale. However, a lack of promotion may also result in poor worker morale, which can then cause dissatisfaction, resignation, and a decline in performance. Also regular payment of salary can also impact on academic staff performance level in a positive way. When the salary of an academic staff is been paid on a regular basis the staff will be able to meet up with his basic demands in life and as such will be very happy and carry out his duties efficiently which will mean an increase in his performance. Perekeme (2020) Opined that job autonomy gives the academic staff the free hand to carry out his responsibility. He believes that when academic staff are given job autonomy they tend to be at their very best which will increase their job performance. Good pay is also one big motivational factor that enhances workers performance. When workers are properly paid for carrying out their duty, they will be very happy. When workers are happy it will definitely reflect on their performance positively. That is why the issue of good pay should be taken very seriously in the enhancement of staff performance, On the other hand, if workers are not well paid it tend to reduce their morale to work. This will no doubt affect their productivity level negatively.

According to Ngu (2002) fringe benefits in form of financial and other incentives could also motivate to work harder. If they know that increase in their productivity level will attract financial benefits, they will always want to work very hard. This is indeed a very positive way of motivating staff for increased productivity. Also conducive working environment and good health care facilities can be a very good motivational factor for academic staff. When they have a good and conducive working environment, they will always be very happy to carry out their duties. Also when the health care facilities in the university is top-notch, academic staff tend to feel very happy, thereby giving their best and increasing their level of productivity. According to Out (2012) the importance of training and development cannot be over emphasized. That is why staff, especially academic staff need to be constantly trained and developed. When this is done very well academic staff will always be at their very best and give out very good performance. Working condition is very key in increasing the productivity level of academic staff in Nigerian universities, particularly the Niger Delta University.

Statement of Problem

The issue of academic staff poor working condition has been one very big problem that has not been given the seriousness it deserves. Most academic staff in Nigerian universities generally and the Niger Delta University in particular are not really happy because of their poor working condition. There are myriads of issues when it comes to their working condition. These issues range from poor working environment including health care facilities, lack of proper motivation like regular payment of salary, regular promotion, good pay and lack of adequate training and development. These issues no doubt have affected the performance of academic staff negatively, thereby decreasing their level of productivity. But if these issues are properly looked at and handled it could just be a good remedy to increase academic staff performance in Nigerian University particularly, the Niger Delta University.

Purpose of the study

The primary goal of the study is to ascertain the association between academic staff working condition and their performance in the Niger Delta University. Specifically, the objectives are to:

- 1) Examine the extent to which working environment enhances academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University.
- 2) Examine the extent to which motivation enhances academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University.
- 3) Investigate the extent to which training and development enhances academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University.

Research Questions

The following research questions were also drawn to guide the study:

- 1) To what extent does conducive working environment enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University?
- 2) To what extent does motivation enhance the job performance of academic staff in the Niger Delta University?
- 3) To what extent does training and development enhance the job performance of academic staff in the Niger Delta University?

Method

In order to gather data from a representative sample of the community and generalise the results to the full population, this research employed the descriptive survey approach. The whole 872 academic staff members of Niger Delta University comprised the study's population. A sample of 174 academic staff were drawn using the simple random sampling technique. This figure represents 20% of the entire population. A Questionnaire titled The Impact of Working Condition on Academic Staff Job Performance in the Niger Delta University (TIWCASJPNDU) developed by the researcher was used for the collection of data. The instrument was formatted on a four point likert scale: Very High, High, Low, and Very Low extent. Three experts in measurement and

evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations in the Niger Delta University validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was established using test re-test method and the two sets of scores were correlated using Pearson’s Product Movement Correlation (PPMC) Technique to obtain a reliability of 0.73 which therefore means that the instrument was reliable. Frequency count and simple percentage were the statistical tools used for the data analysis.

Result

Research Question 1: To what extent does conducive working environment enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University?

Table 1: Frequency and percentage extent to which conducive working environment enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University.

	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
1	To what extent does good office space enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?	90 51.72%	60 34.48%	14 8.04%	10 5.76%
2	To what extent does conducive classrooms for the purpose of teaching enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?	95 54.60%	57 32.80%	12 6.90%	10 5.76%
3	To what extent does good Laboratory for the purpose of carrying out experiment enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University?	80 45.98%	60 34.48%	22 12.64%	12 6.90%
4	To what extent does well furnished and conducive Library for the purpose of reading and research enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University?	92 52.87%	58 33.33%	18 10.34%	6 3.46%
	Grand Percentage	51.29%	33.77%	9.48%	5.47%

Table 1 presents the findings regarding respondents' perceptions of the impact of adequate office space on academic staff job performance at Niger Delta University. Among the respondents, 90 (45%) believed that such space enhanced performance to a very high extent, 60 (34.48%) to a high extent, 14 (8.04%) to a low extent, and 10 (5.76%) to a very low extent. In addition, 95 (54.60%) of the respondents indicated that learning-friendly classrooms improve the job performance of

academic staff members to an extremely high degree; 57 (32.8%) said it improves their performance to a high degree; 12 (6.9%) said it improves their performance to a low degree; and 10 (5.76%) said it improves their performance to an extremely low degree. Furthermore, among the respondents, 80 individuals (45.98%) held the belief that a fully equipped laboratory for conducting experiments significantly enhances the job performance of academic staff. Of the total, 60 individuals (34.48%) believed that this improvement was substantial, while 22 individuals (12.64%) considered it to be of moderate importance, and 12 individuals (6.90%) considered it to be of extremely minimal importance. In conclusion, 92 participants (52.87%) held the belief that the presence of a properly furnished and conducive library for reading and research significantly enhances the job performance of academic staff to an exceptionally high degree. Additionally, 58 participants (33.33%) shared this view, while 18 participants (10.34%) held the opinion that it improves performance to a moderate degree, and 6 participants (3.46%) believed that it improves performance to an extremely low degree.

Research Question 2: To what extent does motivation enhance the job performance of academic staff of the Niger Delta University?

Table 2: Frequency and percentage on how motivation enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University

	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
5	To what extent does good staff welfare package enhance academic staff job performance In the Niger Delta University?	100 57.47%	50 28.74%	20 11.49%	4 2.30%
6	To what extent does research grants and aids from the government enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University?	90 51.72%	60 34.48%	20 11.49%	4 2.30
7	To what extent does regular promotion enhance academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University?	110 63.21%	50 28.74%	10 5.75%	4 2.30%
8	To what extent does regular payment of salary enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?	100 57.47%	60 34.48%	8 4.60%	6 3.45%
	Grand Percentage	57.47%	31.61%	8.33%	2.59%

According to the data presented in Table 2, one hundred respondents (57.47%) believed that a good staff welfare package enhanced the academic staff's job performance at Niger Delta University to an extremely high degree. Additionally, fifty respondents (28.74%) regarded this as an improvement to a high degree, twenty respondents (11.49) as a reduction in performance, and four respondents (2.30%) as a very small reduction in performance. Ninety (51.72%) of the respondents believed that government research grants and assistance improved the job performance of academic staff to an extremely high extent. Sixty (34.48%) believed that it improved performance to a high extent, while twenty (11.49%) believed it improved performance to a low extent. Four (2.30%) respondents believed that it improved performance to a very low extent. Also 100 (57.47%) of the respondents were of the opinion that regular promotion enhances the job performance of academic staff of the Niger Delta University to a Very High Extent, 50 (28.74%) were of the opinion that it enhances their performance to a High Extent, 10 (5.75%) were of the opinion that it enhances their performance to a Low Extent, while 4 (2.30) of the respondents were of the opinion that it enhances their performance to a Very Low Extent. In conclusion, a total of 100 respondents (57.47%) held the view that regular salary disbursement significantly improves the job performance of academic staff at Niger Delta University to an exceptionally high degree. Sixty respondents (34.48%) believed that this improvement was to a high degree, 8 respondents (4.60%) said it was to a low degree, and 6 respondents (3.45%) said it was to an extremely low degree.

Research Question 3: To what extent does training and development enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?

Table 3 Frequency and percentage on how Training and Development enhances academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University.

	Item	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
9	To what extent does seminar enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?	80 45.99%	60 34.48%	20 11.49%	14 8.04
10	To what extent does workshop enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?	90 51.72%	50 28.74%	24 13.80%	10 5.74%
11	To what extent does conferences enhance academic staff performance in Niger Delta University?	80 45.98%	70 40.22	12 6.90%	12 6.90%

12	To what extent does refresher courses enhance academic staff performance in the Niger Delta University?	95 54.60%	55 31.61%	18 10.34%	6 3.45
	Grand Average	49.57%	33.76%	10.63%	6.04%

Eighty (45.99%) of the respondents (Table 3) believed that seminar significantly improved the performance of academic staff at Niger Delta University to a very high extent. Sixty (34.34%) of the respondents believed that the seminar significantly improved their performance to a high degree. Twenty respondents (11.49%) held the view that it marginally improves their performance, whereas fourteen (8.04%) expressed the view that it significantly diminishes it. In addition, a total of 90 (51.72%) of the respondents held the view that sending academic staff to workshops significantly improves their performance. Among those who agreed, 50 (28.74%) said it improves performance to a high extent, 24 (13.80%) said it improves performance to a low extent, and 10 (5.74%) said it improves performance to an extremely low extent. A total of 80 respondents (45.98%) held the view that conference attendance has a very high impact on the job performance of academic staff at Niger Delta University. Of the remaining 12 respondents (6.90%), 70 (40.22%) expressed the opinion that conference attendance has a high impact on their performance, and 12 (4.58%) held the view that it has a low impact on their performance. In summary, the responses indicate that 95 (54.60%) of the participants believed that academic staff refresher courses at Niger Delta University improve their job performance to an exceptionally high degree, 55 (31.61%) said that it improves performance to a high degree, 18 (10.34) said that it improves performance to a low degree, and 6 (3.45) said that it improves performance to an extremely low degree.

Discussion

The study revealed that working condition has a very big importance on academic staff job performance. Table 1 shows that an average of 51.29% and 33.77 of the respondents were of the opinion that conducive working environment enhances academic job performance in the Niger Delta University to a Very High Extent (VHE) and High Extent (HE) respectively, while an average of 9.48% and 5.47% of the respondents were of the opinion that it enhances their performance to a low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). This means that conducive working environment enhances workers job performance significantly and positively.

Table 2 indicates that an average of 57.47% of the respondents believes that motivation enhances academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University to a very High Extent (VHE) and High Extent (HE), while 8.33% and 2.59% believes that it enhances their performance to a Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). This implies that motivation impacts academic staff job performance in a significant and positive way. Table 3 shows that an average of 49.57% and 33.76% of the respondents were of the opinion that Training and Development enhance academic

staff job performance in the Niger Delta University to a Very High Extent (VHE) and High Extent (HE) respectively, while 10.63 and 6.04 were of the opinion that it enhances performance their job performance to a Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). This also indicates that Training and Development impacts academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University significantly and positively.

Conclusion

This study has been able to reveal that good working condition significantly and positively impact academic staff job performance in the Niger Delta University through the provision of conducive working environment, very good motivational incentives as well as regular training and development.

Recommendation

The study's findings influenced the formulation of the following recommendations:

- In order for Niger Delta University's academic staff to perform exceptionally well, the institution should provide a conducive working environment consisting of well-appointed laboratories, conducive workspaces, and adequate library facilities.
- In order to ensure optimal performance by the academic staff of Niger Delta University, it is imperative that they are adequately motivated. This can be achieved by providing competitive welfare packages, research grants and aids, regular promotion opportunities, and regular salary disbursements.
- Consistent training and development of the academic staff at Niger Delta University through participation in renewal courses, seminars, and conferences would enable them to maintain their expertise and operate at their highest level.

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